

ORACLE MAXIMUM SECURITY ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract

Oracle Database Vault (ODBV) user security issues concerning the rules of creation and its features superior to password protection. The use of ODBV in the banking sector was discussed. Oracle database administrators (ODBA) in the banking sector were informed about the problems that ODBA can cause and the importance of protecting confidential information. The Oracle Database (ODB) is one of the databases that stores information. It has database and user security to keep information confidential in ODB. It is critical in both the banking and financial sectors.

Keywords: Oracle Database Vault, software, hardware, management systems.

Oracle is a leading provider of enterprise software and hardware solutions, including database management systems that are used by organizations to manage and secure their data. Oracle provides a range of technologies that can be used to enhance data security, and these technologies can be grouped into four categories based on their characteristics:

1. **Access Control Technologies:** These technologies are designed to control access to data and prevent unauthorized access. Access control technologies include tools such as authentication and authorization mechanisms, identity and access management solutions, and single sign-on capabilities.

2. **Data Protection Technologies:** These technologies are designed to protect data from unauthorized access, modification, or destruction. Data protection technologies include encryption and tokenization solutions, data masking and obfuscation techniques, and backup and recovery mechanisms.

3. **Monitoring and Auditing Technologies:** These technologies are designed to monitor and audit data access and usage, and to detect and respond to security incidents. Monitoring and auditing technologies include security information and event management (SIEM) solutions, log management tools, and network and endpoint security solutions.

4. **Compliance and Governance Technologies:** These technologies are designed to ensure compliance with regulatory and industry standards, and to manage and enforce security policies and procedures. Compliance and governance technologies include policy and risk management solutions, security assessment and testing tools, and vulnerability management and patching solutions.

The technologies for each group are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Oracle DB's user security orientation

By using a combination of access control, data protection, monitoring and auditing, and compliance and governance technologies, organizations can enhance their data security and protect their sensitive data from cyber threats.

ODB is a powerful and widely used database management system that stores and manages data for organizations of all sizes. To ensure user security in Oracle DB, the following orientation can be employed:

- **Authentication and Authorization:** Oracle DB supports various authentication and authorization mechanisms, including password-based authentication, role-based access control, and fine-grained access control. These mechanisms can be used to ensure that only

authorized users can access the database and that they are granted access only to the data they need.

- **Encryption:** Oracle DB supports various encryption techniques, including transparent data encryption (TDE), which can be used to encrypt data at rest and in transit. TDE ensures that sensitive data is protected from unauthorized access and can be decrypted only by authorized users.

- **Patching and Upgrades:** Oracle DB releases security patches and updates regularly to address known vulnerabilities and improve database security. It is essential to apply these patches and upgrades to ensure that the database is protected against known security threats.

- Best Practices: Oracle provides various best practices for securing the database, such as creating strong passwords, disabling unnecessary features, restricting access to the database, and regularly backing

up the database. These best practices can help to enhance the security of the database and protect it from cyber threats.

Figure 2. Depicts the Oracle Maximum security architecture.

Organizations may assure the confidentiality of their Oracle DB while safeguarding their private information from hacking attempts by using these safety precautions.

ODB Firewall is a security solution that provides real-time database activity monitoring and blocking capabilities to prevent unauthorized access, SQL injection attacks, and other threats to the ODB. It acts as a proxy between the database and the application, intercepting all database traffic and enforcing security policies to prevent malicious activity [9].

ODBF uses a combination of signature-based and behavioral analysis techniques to identify and block unauthorized access attempts and malicious SQL queries. It can also monitor user activity and generate alerts when suspicious activity is detected, allowing security administrators to investigate and respond to potential security incidents.

Some of the key features and benefits of ODBF include:

- Real-time monitoring and blocking of database traffic: ODBF provides real-time monitoring of database traffic and can block unauthorized access and SQL injection attacks in real-time.
- Customizable security policies: ODBF allows security administrators to create and customize security policies based on specific needs and requirements.
- Centralized management: ODBF provides centralized management of security policies, alerts, and reports, making it easy to manage and monitor database security across multiple databases and environments.
- Regulatory compliance: ODBF helps organizations comply with regulatory requirements such as PCI DSS, HIPAA, and SOX by providing audit logs and reports.
- Reduced risk of data breaches: ODBF reduces the risk of data breaches by blocking unauthorized access attempts and SQL injection attacks, protecting sensitive data stored in the database.

Figure 3. Oracle Database Firewall

ODBF is a powerful security solution that can help organizations enhance their database security and protect their sensitive data from cyber threats.

Oracle Virtual Private Database (VPD) is a security feature that provides fine-grained access control to data stored in an ODB. VPD enables organizations to enforce data access policies based on user roles, responsibilities, and other attributes, providing a high level of security and control over sensitive data.

VPD works by dynamically modifying SQL statements at run time, based on the policies defined by the

administrator. This allows VPD to control access to data at the row and column level, ensuring that users can only access the data they are authorized to access.

Some of the key features and benefits of Oracle VPD include:

- Fine-grained access control: Oracle VPD provides fine-grained access control to data, allowing administrators to enforce data access policies based on user roles, responsibilities, and other attributes.

- Dynamic security policies: Oracle VPD allows administrators to define and modify security policies dynamically, providing a high degree of flexibility and control over data access.
- Transparent to applications: Oracle VPD is transparent to applications, which means that applications do not need to be modified to work with VPD.
- Improved performance: Oracle VPD can improve database performance by reducing the number of database queries required to retrieve data.
- Enhanced security: Oracle VPD enhances database security by enforcing data access policies at the row and column level, reducing the risk of unauthorized data access.

Oracle Virtual Private Database (VPD) has three main components, which are:

1. Security Policy: A security policy is a set of rules and conditions that are defined by the administrator to control data access. The policy is defined using SQL statements or PL/SQL code and is associated with a database table or view.

2. Security Function: A security function is a PL/SQL function that is defined by the administrator and is used to enforce the security policy. The function is invoked by the ODB at run time to dynamically modify SQL statements to enforce the security policy.

3. Application Context: An application context is a set of attributes that are defined by the administrator to identify the current user and other relevant session information. The attributes are stored in a context namespace and can be used to enforce the security policy.

These three components work together to enforce data access policies based on user roles, responsibilities, and other attributes. The security policy defines the rules and conditions for data access, the security function enforces the policy by modifying SQL statements at run time, and the application context provides the user and session information necessary to enforce the policy.

To create a generating function with a dynamic WHERE clause and add a security policy to it in ODB, you can follow these steps:

1. Create the generating function: The generating function will be used to dynamically generate a WHERE clause for the SELECT statement based on the input arguments (schema and object names). Here is an example of a generating function:

```
CREATE OR REPLACE FUNCTION
get_where_clause(p_schema_name IN VARCHAR2,
p_object_name IN VARCHAR2)
RETURN VARCHAR2
IS
v_where_clause VARCHAR2(1000);
BEGIN
v_where_clause := 'WHERE owner = ' ||
p_schema_name || ' AND object_name = ' || p_ob-
ject_name || ''';
RETURN v_where_clause;
END;
```

This function takes two input arguments (p_schema_name and p_object_name) and returns a

VARCHAR2 value containing the WHERE clause for the SELECT statement.

2. Create the security policy: The security policy will use the generating function to dynamically generate the WHERE clause for the SELECT statement and enforce data access policies based on user roles and privileges. Here is an example of a security policy:

```
BEGIN
DBMS_RLS.ADD_POLICY(
object_schema => 'security_administrator',
object_name => 'surveys',
policy_name => 'surveys_security_policy',
function_schema => 'security_administrator',
policy_function => 'get_where_clause',
statement_types => 'SELECT, INSERT,
UPDATE, INDEX, DELETE',
update_check => TRUE,
enable => TRUE
);
END;
```

This policy applies to the 'surveys' table in the 'security_administrator' schema and uses the 'get_where_clause' function to dynamically generate the WHERE clause for the SELECT statement. The policy applies to SELECT, INSERT, UPDATE, INDEX, and DELETE commands and performs an update check to ensure that users can only modify data that they are authorized to modify. The policy is enabled by setting the 'enable' parameter to TRUE.

By creating a generating function and adding a security policy to it, you can enforce fine-grained data access control in ODB based on user roles, privileges, and other attributes. The combination of these three components provides a powerful and flexible mechanism for enforcing fine-grained data access control in

VPD provides several useful features for data security and access control in ODB, including:

- Fine-grained access control: VPD allows administrators to define fine-grained access control policies based on user roles, responsibilities, and other attributes. This allows for more precise control over data access and ensures that users can only access the data that they are authorized to access.

- Dynamic data masking: VPD can be used to dynamically mask sensitive data based on user roles or other criteria. This ensures that sensitive data is not exposed to unauthorized users, even if they have access to the database.

- Row-level security: VPD can be used to enforce row-level security, which means that users can only access specific rows of data within a table. This is useful for multi-tenant applications or other scenarios where users should only be able to access their own data.

- Consistent security across applications: VPD provides a consistent security model across all applications that access the database. This ensures that data access policies are enforced consistently, regardless of the application used to access the data.

- Easy to implement: VPD is easy to implement and can be configured using SQL statements or PL/SQL code. This makes it easy to integrate into existing applications and workflows.

Oracle VPD provides a powerful and flexible mechanism for enforcing data access control and ensuring data security in ODB . Its fine-grained access control, dynamic data masking, row-level security, and ease of implementation make it a valuable tool for organizations that need to protect sensitive data and ensure compliance with data privacy regulations.

OLS is a security feature of ODB that provides a high-level security model for data protection. It enables administrators to define security policies based on data classifications, which are represented by labels. These labels are attached to rows in database tables and can be used to enforce data access control and data protection policies. OLS provides the following features:

- Label-based access control: OLS allows administrators to define access control policies based on labels. Users can only access data with labels that match their clearance level. For example, users with a "top secret" clearance level can only access data with a "top secret" label.
- Label-based data protection: OLS can be used to protect data based on labels. For example, data with a "top secret" label can be encrypted, while data with a "public" label may not require any encryption.
- Policy-based control: OLS enables administrators to define policies for data access and data protection. These policies can be based on data classifications, user roles, and other criteria.
- Easy to use: OLS is easy to use and can be integrated with existing Oracle security features such as roles and privileges.

To create a policy in OLS, which can be applied to the schedule, you need to perform the following steps:

1. Identify the data that needs to be protected: Determine which tables or columns in your database contain sensitive data that needs to be protected.
2. Define data classifications: Determine how you want to classify your data. For example, you might classify data as "public," "internal," or "confidential."
3. Create labels: Create labels that correspond to your data classifications. For example, you might create a label called "confidential" to correspond to your most sensitive data.
4. Create a security policy: Create a security policy that defines how data access should be controlled based on labels. You can use the Oracle Label Security Administrator tool to create the policy.

5. Assign labels to data: Assign labels to the tables or columns in your database that contain sensitive data.

6. Test the policy: Test the policy to ensure that it is working as expected.

7. Apply the policy to the schedule: Once the policy is working as expected, you can apply it to the schedule. This will ensure that the policy is enforced on a regular basis.[10]

By following these steps, you can create a policy in Oracle Label Security that can be applied to the schedule, ensuring that your sensitive data is protected against unauthorized access or disclosure. OLS is particularly useful for organizations that handle sensitive or confidential data, such as government agencies, financial institutions, and healthcare providers. It provides a high-level security model that is designed to protect data against unauthorized access, disclosure, or modification.

Oracle Audit Vault(OAV) is a security solution that provides a centralized repository for audit data from various sources, including ODB, operating systems, and third-party applications. It enables organizations to collect and analyze audit data from multiple sources in real-time, providing a comprehensive view of security events across the enterprise. OAV provides the following features:

- Centralized audit data collection: Audit data from various sources is collected and stored in a centralized repository, providing a single location for analysis and reporting.
- Real-time alerts: OAV can generate real-time alerts when security events occur, allowing organizations to respond quickly to potential threats.
- Comprehensive reporting: OAV provides a range of reporting capabilities, including customizable dashboards, pre-built reports, and ad-hoc reporting.
- Auditing compliance: OAV supports auditing compliance with industry standards such as PCI DSS, HIPAA, and SOX.
- Secure storage: Audit data is securely stored in the Audit Vault repository, providing protection against unauthorized access and tampering.
- Integration with ODB : OAV can be integrated with ODB to provide additional security features such as database firewall and database activity monitoring.

The high-level design of Oracle Audit Vault is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Architecture of Oracle Audit Vault

The high-level architecture of OAV consists of three main components:

- Oracle AV Server: This component is the central management platform for Oracle Audit Vault. It provides a web-based interface for configuring and managing audit policies, alerts, and reports. It also includes the audit data repository, which stores the audit data collected from AV agents.

- Oracle AV Agents: These are lightweight software components that are installed on the target database servers or other systems to be audited. The agents collect audit data from the target systems and send it to the Audit Vault collector.

- Oracle AV Collector: This component collects the audit data from the agents and sends it to the Audit Vault Server. The collector can be installed on a separate system or co-located with the Audit Vault Server.

Together, these components provide a comprehensive auditing and compliance reporting solution for enterprise systems. The agents are responsible for collecting audit data from the target systems, the collector is responsible for transmitting the data to the Audit Vault Server, and the server is responsible for storing and managing the data and generating compliance reports.

OAV is particularly useful for organizations that need to comply with regulatory requirements, such as those in the financial services, healthcare, and government sectors. It provides a centralized, real-time view of security events across the enterprise, enabling organizations to identify and respond to potential threats quickly and efficiently.

References

1. Flex solutions Ltd, "Oracle-database-vault-with-iflex", 2008, p.320-347;
2. Dan Norris, "Configuring System privileges and Role authorization", London, TUCS, 2012, p.106-180;
3. David Knox, "Effective Oracle Database 10g Security by Design" 2004, p.100-198;
4. Scott Gaetjen, David Knox, William Maroulis, "Oracle Database 12c Security", 2015, p.161-199;
5. Donald K. Burleson, "Oracle Privacy Security Auditing", 2012, p.101-178;
6. K.Gopalakrishnan, "Oracle Database 12c Release 2", Oracle Real Application Clusters Handbook: Concepts, Administration, Tuning & Troubleshooting, 2010, p.101-131
7. Steven Feuerstein, Bill Pribyl, "Oracle PL/SQL programming", 2013, p.12-98.